

ESG KEY TO SUSTAINABLE REPORTING - AN IMPACT FACTOR ON
PERFORMANCE OF NIFTY COMPANIES

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Abstract:

This research papers aim is to find out the relationship between Financial performance(ROE), market performance(Toblin's Q) and Business performance (ROA)of a company to environmental social Governance rating where return on equity ,Return on assets and Toblin,'s Q are considered as Dependent variables and environmental social governance rating "ESG" is considered as Independent Variable. Companies with higher ESG rating is presumed to be more attractive for the Investors than the companies awarded with lower ESG rating. So the purpose of this research paper is to find out the impact of this ESG rating on Financial, Market and Business Performance of the companies. The findings show that there is no impact on financial performance due to ESG Factors

Key Words: Sustainability, ESG, Return on Assets, Toblin's Q

Introduction

Corporate sustainability in today's business environment is supported by three fundamental principles: financial integrity, equality for all, and the preservation of the environment. It is acknowledged that the sum of these elements enables businesses to turn a profit through achieving productivity, maximization of shareholder value, and long-term objectives.

On the other hand, a company's inefficient administration of social, environmental, and governance risks can hurt its image in the market, have an adverse effect on the company's financial status, and obstruct its long-term expansion

Consequently, extra-financial reporting is necessary to strengthen sustainable growth of companies and include information on position in society defined by its activity. Sustainability reporting is the means by which companies reveal the degree to which they have had an impact on their physical, social and economic environment. Under "environmental disclosure", a company provides information about the impacts of its operations on environment which includes all three environmental resources that is air, water, land.. The "social disclosure" provides information about the effect on social systems, including employees, customers, suppliers and the community as a whole. The "economic communication" of sustainability informs about an organization's economic and its likely impact at national and international scale.

Global Reporting Initiatives

An independent, global organisation called "Global Reporting Initiative," with its main office in Amsterdam, Netherlands, assists companies in using a universal language to convey the effects of their business activities on the environment, the economy, and society. The Sustainability nonfinancial reporting standards which are being used most all over the world are GRI standards. They are followed by almost 94% of the world's largest 340 corporates across 100 countries (GRI Standards, 2021).

Indian Reporting Initiatives

In India, sustainability reporting norms have evolved over the years to keep pace with global standards and home considerations. The year 2007 saw a modest beginning when the Reserve Bank of India advised all commercial banks to disclose information on their CSR efforts. In 2011, the "Ministry of corporate affairs" issued guidelines on Environmental, Social, and Economic responsibilities of business via "National Voluntary Guidelines (NVGs)"

These guidelines were advisory in nature and suggested the broad principles and structure on which sustainability reports should be based. In 2012 "security exchange board of India (SEBI) "issued a Circular on Coporate Responsibility.

As per section 135 of "Companies Act 2013",It is now mandatory for the various companies to spend their 2% of net yearly earning s in CST initiatives. The importance of sustainable and ethical investment techniques has progressively increased from the perspective of investors. With the help of organizations like "the United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative", environmental, social, and governance (ESG) oriented portfolio selection strategies have progressively grown in prominence, among investors under the umbrella of sustainable and responsible investment. The fundamental idea behind ESG-based investing is to discover and quantify the intangible value that companies with strong governance practices and a commitment to social responsibility and the environment hold. . These companies are thought to demonstrate stronger ESG risk management techniques, which in turn generate value for investors through long-term sustainable business models. These ESG indicators, which are numerous and constantly changing, represent an organization's non-financial performance. They consist of:

- Environmental issues include deforestation, resource depletion, climate change, emissions of greenhouse gases, and waste and pollution.
- Social: Conflict, native communities, local and working circumstances that include child labour and slavery, employee relations, safety, diversity, and health.
- Governance: Executive remuneration, Politicization, bribery, donations and corruption, diversity on the board, tax strategy and tax planning and board diversity.

Through collaboration between CRISIL and the NSE India, the ESG Index was introduced in India.

This index's goal is to measure the exposure to assets that meet the standards for sustainable investing. For the developed economies, the volume of literature based on ESG is expanding. The

true state of ESG practises and their effects on businesses in emerging economies have not been well studied. Examining how ESG factors affect performance is the goal of this paper.

It mandated “top 100 listed companies to follow NVGs and to clearly disclose their CSR efforts in Business Responsibility Reports (BRR) which would be part of Annual Reports”. This number increased to 500 in 2015. In 2014, a landmark CSR law was passed through an amendment in the Companies Act which mandated a minimum CSR spending on the part of specified firms. Among other developments in the arena of Non financial disclosures and sustainability reporting , the most recent is the circular issued by The “Securities and Exchange Board of India” in May 2021 which mandated the preparation of a Business Responsibility and Sustainability Report (BRSR) by top 1000 firms, in place of earlier BRR. Other firms are also being encouraged in this regard. Interestingly, although in India many developments have taken place over the years to ensure that businesses adopt and disclose their sustainability practices, there is no uniformity or standardization as to the contents of the reports. There are no specific guidelines that seek to present the relevant non-financial information in a single report. Nevertheless, the results of numerous studies have revealed that the majority of the companies have started reporting on sustainability issues in some form or the other.

Literature review

Impact of the ESG rating on Financial, Market and Business Performance of the companies

A number of studies have attempted to establish a connection between the financial success of an organisation and its corporate sustainability performance, both theoretically and practically. The results to this point have either been inconclusive or contradictory. As a result, the aforementioned work is essentially split into two categories: those that they believe will have either a favourable or negative influence. If investors are specific about the future worth of the firm on the basis of the existing level of environmental responsibility, the company that does not engage in sustainability reporting will experience a decline in the price of its shares.

According to numerous study publications, sustainability reporting, which ultimately results in profit for the organisation, will have a favourable impact on the organization's long-term financial health and return on investment. Businesses that harm the environment may gradually see their revenue decline, which could have an impact on their future solvency. The company's financial success may be impacted by social responsibility efforts. Companies' efforts to promote sustainable development and non-financial disclosure will result in both benefits and costs. Depending on the impact, disclosure, and reporting of the information, there can have a positive or negative influence on the financial performance. Depending on Disclosure and reporting of Business information there may be an favorable or negative impact on financial performance of the company.

There are both Positive and lack of positive relationship, which have been recognized by the various studies between Sustainability performance and economic performance of the company.

There are researchers who support sustainability reporting and nonfinancial disclosures and advocate the system of non-financial reporting to be more transparent and show the link between the financial sector of the corporation and the three parameters of non-financial reporting. There are many research articles that try to unearth the connection between the economic performance of the company and Sustainability rating and these theories relates to the influence and casualty of the relationship.

Amina Buallay (2022) examines the connection between the performance of the retail industry and the extent of sustainability reporting. A dependent manufacturing performance indicator variable is regressed against a variable that is independent and derives from the ESG rating. The conclusions drawn from the empirical studies show that ESG, corporate sustainability, financial performance , operational performance , and Toblin have a significant link.

Camelia Oprean-Stan et al.(2020) This study looked into the favorable and unfavorable linear link between the relationship of company success and sustainable growth, ESG factors and sustainable reporting. The sustainability of firm growth, trade market and financial performance are accessed by the dependent variables whereas, the sustainability metrics and the model-included control variables for these regressions come under Independent Variables. This is all based on how author assess and analyze a company's performance and sustainable growth which is affected by ESG risk management

Amina Mohamed Buallay et.al(2021) This study examined the links between level of sustainability reporting and financial performance in banking sector.

The study by Amina Buallayet al (2020) examined the connection between Gender diversity on boards and sustainable reporting. Gender diversity in boards is partially supported by regression model as a casual component which has prominent favourable effect on ESG rating when 22-50% of Board members are female.

Alexandra A. Egorova et.al(2020) In this study IT Companies were the main focus of the research .The study aimed at evaluating the effect of ESG rating on the Market performance of the various companies .For valuation of market performance ,Toblin Q is taken in to consideration

Karishma K. Dalal et al. (2019) Aim of this paper is to find out the effect of ESG rating on financial performance of Indian public limited companies for which they have used return on assets and Toblin Q as the dependent variables. By using random panel data analysis this study has been conducted .

Amina Bulayy (2019) In order to determine how reporting on “environmental, social, and governance (ESG)” issues affects corporate operations, financial health, and market performance, this study examines ESG reporting levels in the industrial and banking sectors. The fundamental components of the practical model are the independent variable (ESG) and the dependent variables “return on equity”, “return on assets”, and “Tobin's Q”.

Amal AOUADI(2016) This article has looked into the relationship between business market value and “environmental, social, and governance (ESG)”Score. A striking primary analysis demonstrates that ESG factors are linked to higher firm value. When compared to the corporate social performance (CSP) score, it is discovered that ESG controversies have no direct effect on business value, but the interaction seems to be substantial and considerably affirmative.

Ruhaya Atan(2018) In this study, Malaysian public limited corporations' (PLC) profitability, firm value, and cost of capital performance are examined in relation to ESG aspects. The pooled OLS, fixed effect, and random effect panel data regressions were used in this study. Findings The outcome of regression analysis shows that there is no substantial link between return on equity ,Firms value and ESG characteristics Independently or together

Objective of Study

The objective of this Paper is to objectively investigate the impact of ESG on the profitability and firm value of listed Indian enterprises.

Hypothesis Development

It is presumable that businesses with better ESG ratings will attract investors significantly more than those with lower ratings. So, we suggest using the following hypothesis to examine how ESG rating affects Financial, Market performance of the company:

H1. The Corporate’s ESG rating affects its return on assets (ROA).

H2. Toblin's Q of the company is impacted by the company's ESG grade.

H3. A company's ESG grade has an effect on its ROE

Data

For the study, the yearly ESG score for 45 Indian companies listed on the NSE Index database for the period 2022 was taken into account.

The Independent Variables

The independent variables, the ESG factors, are measured using the ESG ratings published by Crisil maintained by NSE India. Index constituents are derived from the top 50 Indian companies listed on the NSE by total market capitalization. . In ESG rating framework, ESG scores—ranging from 0 to 100—measure a company’s relative ESG performance and effectiveness across ten themes focusing on “E”, “S” and “G” pillars based on 630 company-level ESG measures. Out of these 630 data points, a subset of 186 of the most comparable and relevant parameters for each industry are used to in the company’s scoring process.

These data points are grouped into 10 categories under the respective “E”, “S” and “G” heads, which are then used to generate scores on each of these three pillars. The ESG pillar score is a

relative sum of the category weights. While these weights are same across sectors for the Governance category, they vary across sectors for the Environmental and Social categories.

Dependent Variable

Common accounting-based measurements used in research studies examining the effects of ESG compliance include “return on assets “(ROA), “return on equity “(ROE), “return on capital employed” (ROCE), “return on investment “(ROI), total assets (TA), and return on sales (ROS). As a result, the two criteria—profitability and firm value—are used to evaluate the dependent variable, firm performance. As one of the broadest indicators of a company's operating performance, ROA was selected as a measure of profitability. The Capitaline database is used to acquire information on ROA as well as market capitalization and book value of total assets. Tobin's Q has been widely utilised to estimate a firm's market value. The book value of all assets is utilised as a stand-in for the replacement cost of the assets, as per Chung and Pruitt (1994), to determine Tobin's Q value. Additionally, market value is determined by adding market capitalization to the book value of all assets, deducting net worth, and dividing that result by the book value of all assets.

Control Variables:

Leverage and firm size, two common control variables in the literature, are used in this study. A company using leverage uses borrowed money. The ratio of total assets to net worth is used to calculate it. Leverage is considered in this analysis because managers frequently report more ESG data as leverage rises as a result of greater scrutiny from financial institutions. Finally, as prior research has shown that large businesses may prove to be more effective due to their propensity to take advantage of economies of scale, hire more qualified managers, and formalize processes that may improve performance ,size is taken into account as a control variable.

Dependent Variables	
Return on Asset	Net profit/average total assets
Return on Equity	ROE=Shareholder <u>Equity</u> Net Income
Tobin's Q	(Total assets + market capitalization – <u>networth</u>)/Total assets
Independent Variables	
ESG	Environmental, social and governance performance score collected from the NSE 100 ESG Index database
Control Variables	
Leverage	Total assets/ <u>networth</u> (unsystematic firm risk)
Size	Log of total assets (firm size)

Estimation of Models and Empirical Tests

The key techniques and tests used for investigating the data are as follows:

From an examination of the literature, it was determined that Tobin's Q, ROA, and ROI are appropriate metrics for determining a company's market worth. In Olson's [18] description of a model for valuing public enterprises, the market value of capital is established using both financial and additional non-financial information about the company. Olson did not indicate that any non-financial information might be included in the model; hence, we would use ESG data as non-financial information instead.

To test hypothesis H1, the following model was developed:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ROA + \beta_2 ESG \text{ score}$$

Yt - Tobin's Q, calculated as Market value/Book value;
ROA - Return On Assets (Net Profit/Total Assets);
ESG score – the ESG rating

To test hypothesis H2, the following model was developed:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Tobin's Q} + \beta_2 ESG \text{ score}$$

Yt - Tobin's Q, calculated as Market value/Book value;
ROA - Return On Assets (Net Profit/Total Assets);
ESG score – the ESG rating

To test hypothesis H3, the following model was developed:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ROI + \beta_2 ESG \text{ score}$$

Yt - Tobin's Q, calculated as Market value/Book value;
ROI - Return On Assets (Net Profit/Total Assets);
ESG scores – the ESG rating from Crisil

Results and Discussions

Table 1 summarizes the descriptive statistics of our variables, dependent, independent and the control. The mean (median) ESG scores of the sample are 62.71111 (63.00000), whereas those for the financial performance as measured through ROA and Tobin's Q are 0.136670 (0.107119) and 7.674422 (4.104276) respectively. Descriptive statistics for control variables are presented next with a mean (median) of 0.470000 (0.080000) for Leverage and 64924.89 (21151.00) for Size.

Table 1.Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Sum Sq. Deviation
ROE	0.175556	0.150000	0.680000	-0.08	0.864311
ESG	62.71111	63.00000	76.00000	44.00000	2343.244
LEVERAGE	0.470000	0.080000	4.110000	0.000000	31.24940
SIZE	64924.89	21151.00	592195.0	0.000000	5.85E+11
ROA	0.136670	0.107119	0.510311	-0.030914	0.608911
TOBINSQ	7.674422	4.104276	62.12251	0.417817	4715.422

Correlation results

Table 2 presents the dependent, independent, and control variables' Pearson correlation matrix. The firm's ESG score is highly connected with the size of the business but not with ROA or Tobin's Q. Regarding the connection between the regressed parameters and the financial performance variables, the correlation results were equivocal.

Table 2:Correlations

		ESG	Tobin's Q	ROA	SIZE
ESG	Pearson Correlation	1	.041	.107	0.355585
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.787	.482	0.0165
Tobin's Q	Pearson Correlation	.041	1	.262	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.787		.082	
ROA	Pearson Correlation	.107	.262	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.482	.082		
Size	Pearson Correlation	.107	.262	1	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.482	.082		
<p>Note: * indicates correlation significance at the 0.05 level and ** indicates correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.</p>					

Regression Results

For the dependent variables, ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q, respectively, the results of the random effects simple regression model are summarised in Tables 3, 4, and 5. The random effects model was used to get the estimated coefficients, t-statistics, and p values that are displayed in Tables 3 and 4 for the dependent variables ROA and Tobin's Q, respectively.

The coefficient column shows how much the independent variable contributes in predicting the variation in the dependent variable provided the other predictor variables remain constant. The values of coefficient read with the p value indicate a significant positive relation at 0.05 level between the ESG scores on both, the dependent variables, ROA and Tobin's Q . As compared to this, the control variables, whether Leverage or Size, do not materially affect the dependent variables. The relationship of the dependent and the predictor variable, as established through the model, is represented through the following equations:

$$ROA_{it} = 0.024004 + (0.001797) ESG_{it}$$

$$ROE_{it} = 0.024004 + (0.001797) ESG_{it}$$

$$\text{Tobin's } Q_{it} = 3.990322 + (0.058747) ESG_{it}$$

Table 3: Regression ROE and ESG

	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Statistic	P
Constant	0.024004	0.154213	0.155655	0.8770
ESG	0.001797	0.002443	0.735411	0.4661
Mean Dependent Var	64924.89		SD Dependent Var	115264.5
Sum Squared Resid	5.11E+11		SE of Regression	108976.8
Log-Likelihood	-584.7794		Akaike Criterion	26.07908
Schwarz Criterion	26.15938		Hannan-Quinn	26.10902
Note: * indicates correlation significance at the 0.05 level and ** indicates correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.				

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P
Constant	-0.137761	0.184790	-0.745499	0.4600
ESG	-0.000603	0.002927	-0.205877	0.8379
Mean Dependent Var	-0.175556		SD Dependent Var	0.140155
Sum Squared Resid	0.863460		SE of Regression	0.141706
Log-Likelihood	-25.10085		Akaike Criterion	1.026704
Schwarz Criterion	-0.946408		Hannan-Quinn	-0.996771
Note: * indicates correlation significance at the 0.05 level and ** indicates correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.				

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P
Constant	3.990322	13.64411	0.292457	0.7713
ESG	0.058747	0.216145	0.271796	0.7871
Mean Dependent Var	7.674422		SD Dependent Var	10.35223
Sum Squared Resid	4707.334		SE of Regression	10.46293
Log-Likelihood	-168.4821		Akaike Criterion	7.576981
Schwarz Criterion	7.657277		Hannan-Quinn	7.606914
Note: * indicates correlation significance at the 0.05 level and ** indicates correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.				

Conclusion

From the standpoint of India, this study significantly expands upon previous research in the area of ESG effects. According to the results of the descriptive research over a year, better ESG scores have no appreciable impact on the financial performance of organisations. Compared to earlier research, this one uses procedures with higher procedural accuracy. In addition to accounting metrics, which are seen as a short-term performance report, the financial performance of the company is also evaluated in terms of market indicators, which are seen as a gauge of long-term firm performance. The analysis is made more comprehensive by using a variety of metrics to assess financial success. This adds significantly to the already completed work. The conclusions have immediate implications for governments, investors, regulators, and Indian companies.

Limitations and Scope for Future Research

One year may not be enough time to fully understand the effect of ESG on a company's financial success; a longer period of research may be necessary. One-year ESG scores might not accurately represent the genuine ESG practises of businesses. The study's final drawback is the potential impact of additional factors, such as competition and corporate environment, on company financial success.

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